

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of a Bond Isomer of Calacone*

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Calacone (IIb) is an unsaturated sesquiterpene ketone which was recently isolated from sweet-flag oil by Sörm and Herout¹. In the present communication we report the synthesis of isocalacone (IIa) which is a bond isomer of (IIb) and differs from it in the position of the double bond in the side chain.

The unsaturated ketone (I) was obtained from the methyl ether of carvacrol by the modified metal-ammonia reduction as reported by Dupont and Crabbe². The ketone (I) was submitted to alkylation with 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene, obtained from isoprene and gaseous hydrobromic acid, in presence of sodium amylate to afford (IIa) in 30% yield³. The ultraviolet absorption of the synthetic ketone (IIa) shows peak at $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$, 246m μ (log ϵ , 3.92), which is indicative of trialkyl-substituted $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketonic system.⁴

6-Methyl-2-isopropylcyclohex-2-enone (I) was prepared essentially according to the method mentioned before. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 10.4. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$, C, 79.0; H, 10.6%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone formed bright red needles from ethyl acetate-ethanol, m.p. 165°. (Found: N, 17.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$: N, 16.86%).

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses are done by Drs. Weiler and Strause, Oxford.

1. *Coll. Cze. Chem. Comm.*, 1961, 26, 1021, 1343.

2. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1955, 821.

3. Cf. Conia, *ibid.*, 1954, 943.

4. Fieser and Fieser, 'Natural Products Related to Phenanthrone', Reinhold, 1949, p. 192.

6-Methyl-3-isopropyl-2-(Δ^2 -isopentenyl)-cyclohex-2-enone (IIa).—To a cooled mixture of carvenone (I) (20.0 g., 0.12 *M*) and 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene (25.0 g., 0.16 *M*) in anhydrous ether (150 ml) was added, with constant stirring, a benzene suspension of sodium (2.73 g., 0.12 *M*), dissolved in amyl¹ alcohol (20 ml). The contents were heated at 50° for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with water. The organic phase was removed and the aqueous layer extracted four times with ether. The combined extracts were dried over sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the residual oil was distilled in vacuum to furnish a colorless oil, b.p. 70°/5 mm., yield 6 g. (30%), n_D^{26} 1.5075. (Found: C, 81.35; H, 10.83. $C_{15}H_{24}O$ requires C, 81.81; H, 10.90%).

I. R. absorption spectra in CCl_4 showed characteristic peaks for the synthetic ketone (IIa) at 2975, 2925, 1664, 1450, 1378, 1210 and 895 cm^{-1} .

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